

The Claims Network: Aggregating Traditional & Non-Traditional Scholarly Contributions Using Mastodon

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Abstract. We introduce the Claims Network: an open, decentralized architecture that uses platforms such as Mastodon to register traditional and non-traditional scholarly contributions. IMEC-IDLab (Belgium) and SURF (Netherlands) developed an open-source prototype supporting verification, selection, metadata summarization and Linked Data generation of URL-identified traditional and non-traditional research contributions, irrespective of whether they have a persistent identifier, or not.

Conference Themes: Open infrastructures for responsible research assessment, Recognition of contributions to Open Science

Keywords: Aggregation, Non-Traditional Research Artifacts, Social Networks

1 Background

Global initiatives advocate in favor of recognizing a wider range of scholarly contributions beyond traditional outputs like journal articles and books. Efforts such as DORA [1] and CoARA [2] advocate for including non-traditional outputs—including research data, software, presentations, and media appearances—in assessments of researcher excellence. This broader view is echoed in the 2020 Dutch position paper *Room for Everyone's Talent* [3], which calls for a modernized recognition system across Research, Education, Impact, and Leadership (REIL).

Identifying non-traditional REIL contributions presents a significant challenge, as these contributions are scattered across the Web at large [4-8]. They often lack persistent identifiers such as DOIs and rarely mention the researchers' ORCIDs. This makes systematic discovery difficult within current academic recognition frameworks.

One could ask researchers to manually catalog REIL contributions in research portals, but this creates a considerable burden to collect and annotate metadata. Another method involves monitoring platforms where such contributions may appear, as in the *myresearch.institute* [9] project. However, these platforms are difficult to enumerate, spanning thousands of news outlets, blogs and academic websites.

2 Solution

In 2024, SURF and IMEC-IDLab launched a *Claims Network* to gather REIL contributions using Mastodon [10]. An academic Mastodon operated by SURF offers a platform for informal academic communication on which each researcher's identity is verified using the Dutch academic single sign-on solution SURFconext. Researchers can flag posts (*toots*) that contain REIL content, making the platform a source for tracking scholarly contributions.

For instance, a researcher creates the toot: I was interviewed by NOS about my research! <http://nos.nl/news/1234> @claimbot. Claim (ro)bots in the Claims Network detect such posts and use them to gather metadata about the researcher and the mentioned resource. They generate a REIL claim in RDF, using the schema.org [11] and LDES [12] vocabularies, using a decentralized network of metadata summarization services. These RDF claims can be registered in personalized research profiles and national productivity portals.

3 Results

The Claims Network is an open architecture [13] grounded in decentralized web principles, open standards, and protocols. Its loosely coupled components are reusable beyond research assessment. The prototype implementation is open source and was tested using synthetic data from hundreds of academic Mastodon users. Generation of metadata for REIL claims proved to be especially successful for references to news media. End-user testing is planned for the end of 2025.

We hope the Claims Network inspires similar initiatives—supporting not only responsible, open science-aware research assessment but also fostering a community-owned scholarly communication ecosystem.

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